

Horizon 2020 TWEETHER

Travelling wave tube based w-band wireless networks with high data rate distribution, spectrum & energy efficiency

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WP7.

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PU	Public	X
PP	Restricted to other programme participants (including Commission Services)	
RE	Restricted to a group specified by the consortium (including the Commission Services)	
CO	Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)	

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

TWEETHER consortium is fully aware of the large audience that the “mass media” involve, as well as their power as an efficient and cost-effective way of transmitting information. To this end, two press releases, one at the beginning and one at the end of the project, have been planned to give an adequate visibility to TWEETHER project on the major news sites and newspapers, in the science and tech pages.

This deliverable contains a report on the first press release launched by Lancaster during the first month of the project and how it has been disseminated. Additionally, other actions taken by other partners to advertise the project are covered.

The press release is attached to the document (Annex I) together with another press release developed by UPV press office (Annex II). Finally, some examples of the TWEETHER press release publication in other electronic media are given in Annex III.

1. INTRODUCTION

The objective of the TWEETHER project is set a milestone in the millimetre wave technology with the realization of the first W-band (92-95GHz) wireless system for distribution of high speed internet everywhere. The TWEETHER aim is to realise the millimetre wave Point multi Point segment to finally link fibre, and sub-6GHz distribution for a full three segment hybrid network, that is the most cost-effective architecture to reach mobile or fix final individual client. The TWEETHER system will provide indeed economical broadband connectivity with a capacity up to 10 Gbps and distribution of hundreds of Mbps to tens of terminals. This will allow the capacity and coverage challenges of current backhaul and access solutions to be overcome.

In order to ensure that the TWEETHER project and its innovative approach are successfully promoted to its target audience, the dissemination and communication activities are of great importance for the project partners. The main target audience of the dissemination activities is industry, technical and scientific audience, potential End Users such as telecom operators, interested public and standardization bodies working on the W-band and on definition of Multimedia Wireless Systems (MWS). Moreover, since the European Society as a whole will ultimately benefit from the results of the project (in terms of offering broadband access and new services with high added value such as e-learning, e-health, etc.), special measures will be planned to reach the wide public.

As a first dissemination activity, a press release has been launched by Lancaster as a first step to trigger interest of professional and the society in general for research activities performed in TWEETHER.

2. PRESS RELEASE

A first press release announcing the TWEETHER project was produced by Lancaster to officially launch the project and to make publicity of the kick-off meeting, which was held in Lancaster on the 15th and 16th of January, 2015.

This press release was posted on the News of the Lancaster University website (see Fig. 1) and has been distributed among certain general press magazines and other media, as explained in Section 3.

The following link gives access to the press release, which is also attached in Annex I.

<http://www.lancaster.ac.uk/news/articles/2014/creating-the-fastest-outdoor-wireless-internet-connection-in-the-world/>

The screenshot shows the Lancaster University website. The top navigation bar includes Home, Study, Research, Business, Global, and Alumni. Below the navigation bar, there are statistics: 12,000 students from over 100 countries, and 93% of students go into work or further study within six months of graduating. There are also links for 'Our Colleges', 'News & Blogs', 'About Us', and 'Current Students'. A search bar is present on the right. The main content area features a red sidebar for 'News & Blogs' with links to 'Latest News', 'Latest Blogs', 'The Conversation', and 'Contact the Press Office'. The main article is titled 'Creating the fastest outdoor wireless Internet connection in the world' and is dated 18 December 2014 06:58. The article text describes the TWEETHER project as a ground-breaking £2.8 million project funded by Horizon 2020, aimed at developing a world's first W-band wireless system. A quote on the right states: 'The huge spread of portable smart phone, tablets and the increasing demand of services hungry for data, such as high definition TV, videoconferencing and online games, are posing formidable challenges with the congestion of the available spectrum and the limits of present technology'.

Fig. 1. TWEETHER press release posted on the News section of Lancaster website

Additionally, the UPV has also distributed a press release among several Spanish media. This press release (in Spanish) is enclosed in the Annex II.

On the other hand, in order to increase the visibility of TWEETHER, some partners have included news related to the project on their respective websites, as exemplified below.

- LU Text News Section December 19th: Horizon 2020 TWEETHER Project

The Principal Network Architect of mobile phone giant EE will be the guest speaker at the launch of a new Horizon 2020 project led by Lancaster University. Andy Sutton will address the launch meeting of the Horizon 2020 TWEETHER Project on Thursday 15 January 2015. Professor Claudio Paoloni (Engineering) is to head up this European project team working on the world's first W-band wireless system, heralding the arrival of cost effective, high speed internet everywhere, every time.

Announcement of the kick-off meeting: <http://www.eventbrite.co.uk/e/open-session-kick-off-meeting-horizon-2020-tweether-project-tickets-14503982803>

- UPV: <http://www.ntc.upv.es/proyectos/tweether.html>
- TED will include an article explaining the TWEETHER project in the Thales intranet.

In addition to the actions explained above, it is worth noting that other partners within the TWEETHER consortium will also deliver future press releases.

3. PUBLICATION CHANNELS

As commented previously, apart from the TWEETHER press release posted on the website of the Lancaster University, it has been published in the following electronic media:

- **My Science UK** (<http://www.myscience.org.uk/home/about>)

Creating the fastest outdoor wireless Internet connection in the world

MyScience (Web), 18/12/2014, Unattributed

Lancaster University engineers are to head up a European team working on the world's first W-band wireless system, heralding the arrival of cost effective, high speed internet everywhere, every time.

Reach: 942 visits

Link to the news:

http://www.myscience.org.uk/wire/creating_the_fastest_outdoor_wireless_internet_connection_in_the_world-2014-lancaster&rss=1

- **Alpha Galileo** (<http://www.alphagalileo.org/Default.aspx>)

Creating the fastest outdoor wireless Internet connection in the world

Alpha Galileo (Web), 18/12/2014, Unattributed

Lancaster University engineers are to head up a European team working on the world's first W-band wireless system, heralding the arrival of cost effective, high speed internet everywhere, every time.

Reach: 1662 visits

Link to the news:

<http://www.alphagalileo.org/ViewItem.aspx?ItemId=148384&CultureCode=en>

- **Engineering and Technology Magazine** (<http://eandt.theiet.org/index.cfm>)

World's fastest wireless network to be deployed in Lancaster

Engineering and technology Magazine (Web), 18/12/2014, by Tereza Pultarova

The world's first millimetre wave (W-band) wireless network system will be developed in Lancaster, testing technology that could pave the way for omnipresent cost-effective high-speed Internet.

Reach: 29121 visits

Link to the news: <http://eandt.theiet.org/news/2014/dec/microwave-internet.cfm>

- **Design Products & Application** (<http://www.dpaonthenet.net/>)

Creating the world's fastest outdoor wireless Internet connection

Design Products & Applications (Web), 19/12/2014, Unattributed

Lancaster University engineers are to head up a European team working on the world's first W-band wireless system, heralding the arrival of ubiquitous, high speed internet.

Reach: 3404 visits

Link to the news: <http://www.dpaonthenet.net/article/88426/Creating-the-world-s-fastest-outdoor-wireless-Internet-connection.aspx>

- **PhysOrg.com** (<http://phys.org/>)

Creating the fastest outdoor wireless Internet connection in the world

PhysOrg.com (Web), 19/12/2014, Unattributed

Lancaster University engineers are to head up a European team working on the world's first W-band wireless system, heralding the arrival of cost effective, high speed internet everywhere, every time.

Reach: 156040 visits

Link to the news: <http://phys.org/news/2014-12-fastest-outdoor-wireless-internet-world.html>

- **Computer Business Review** (<http://www.cbronline.com/>)

World's 'fastest wireless network' to arrive in Lancaster

Computer Business Review (Web), 19/12/2014, by Amy-jo Crowley

Scientists are paving the way for the fastest performing Internet at affordable costs.

The first millimetre wave (W-band) wireless network system, said to be the 'world's fastest', is being tested at Lancaster University, paving the way for high-speed Internet at affordable costs.

Reach: 2877 visits

Link to the news: <http://www.cbronline.com/news/tech/networks/networking/worlds-fastest-wireless-network-to-arrive-in-lancaster-4473833>

- **Science 2.0** (<http://www.science20.com/>)

W-Band Wireless: High Speed Internet, Outdoors And Everywhere

Science 2.0 (Blog), 19/12/2014, Unattributed

A European team is working on the world's first W-band wireless system - millimeter wave technology for high speed wireless mobile and fixed point Internet - as part of a £2.8 million TWEETHER project.

Reach: 91158 visits

Link to the news:

http://www.science20.com/news_articles/wband_wireless_high_speed_internet_outdoors_and_everywhere-151636

- **Research & Development** (<http://www.rdmag.com/>)

Creating the fastest outdoor wireless internet connection

Research & Development (Web), 19/12/2014, Unattributed

Lancaster University engineers are to head up a European team working on the world's first W-band wireless system, heralding the arrival of cost effective, high speed internet everywhere, every time.

Reach: 4000 visits

Link to the news: <http://www.rdmag.com/news/2014/12/creating-fastest-outdoor-wireless-internet-connection>

- **BioPortfolio** (<http://www.bioportfolio.com/>)

Creating the fastest outdoor wireless internet connection

BioPortfolio (Web), 19/12/2014, Unattributed

Lancaster University engineers are to head up a European team working on the world's first W-band wireless system, heralding the arrival of cost effective, high speed internet everywhere, every time.

Reach: 3577 visits

Link to the news: <http://www.bioportfolio.com/news/article/2175365/Creating-the-fastest-outdoor-wireless-internet-connection.html>

- **Pan European Networks** (<http://www.paneuropeannetworks.com/>)

H2020 funds high-speed internet development

Pan European Networks (Web), 22/12/2014, Unattributed

UK: Engineers at Lancaster University in the UK are to lead a project developing the world's first W-band wireless system, which will lead to a greater availability of cost-effective, high-speed internet.

Reach: 900 visits

Link to the news: <http://www.paneuropeannetworks.com/science-technology/h2020-funds-high-speed-internet/>

- **World Industrial Reporter** (<http://www.worldindustrialreporter.com/home-2/>)

Lancaster to Create World's First W-Band Outdoor Wireless Internet Connection

World Industrial Reporter (Web), 22/12/2014, Unattributed

Lancaster University will lead a team of EU researchers to develop the world's first W-band wireless system, heralding the arrival of a cost effective, omnipresent and omniscient high speed internet.

Reach: 6000 visits

Link to the news: <http://www.worldindustrialreporter.com/lancaster-create-worlds-first-w-band-outdoor-wireless-system/>

- **RF Globalnet** (<http://www.rfglobalnet.com/>)

Creating The Fastest Outdoor Wireless Internet Connection In The World

RF Globalnet (Web), 23/12/2014, Unattributed

Lancaster University engineers are to head up a European team working on the world's first W-band wireless system, heralding the arrival of cost effective, high speed internet everywhere, every time.

Reach: 300 visits

Link to the news: <http://www.rfglobalnet.com/doc/creating-the-fastest-outdoor-wireless-internet-connection-0001?atc~c=771+s=773+r=001+l=a>

- **ISP Preview** (<http://www.ispreview.co.uk/>)

UK Based TWEETHER Project Promises 10Gbps mmW Wireless Broadband

ISP Preview (Web), 22/01/2015, by Mark Jackson

A team of international scientists working out of Lancaster University in England have officially kicked off a new consortium called TWEETHER, which aims to harness the millimetre wave (mmW) radio spectrum (specifically 92-95GHz) in order to develop a new wireless network that could offer economical broadband connectivity with a capacity up to 10Gbps (Gigabits per second).

Reach: 5500 visits

Link to the news: <http://www.ispreview.co.uk/index.php/2015/01/uk-based-tweether-project-promises-10gbps-mmw-wireless-broadband.html>

- **The Engineer** (<http://www.theengineer.co.uk/>)

W-band wireless broadband system aims to streamline services

The Engineer (Web), 21/01/2015, by Julia Pierce

Rural blackspots and network congestion could end thanks to a new wireless high-speed data communications system under development by a European team led by engineers at Lancaster University.

Estimated reach: 170000 visits

Link to the news: <http://www.theengineer.co.uk/news/w-band-wireless-broadband-system-aims-to-streamline-services/1019762.article#ixzz3Pa91XbWk>

On the other hand, it is worth mentioning that the TWEETHER project has also been announced on the Horizon 2020 Projects website (<http://horizon2020projects.com/>), as shown in Fig. 2.

Fig. 2. The TWEETHER project on the Horizon 2020 Projects website

Link: <http://horizon2020projects.com/il-ict/university-secures-funding-for-major-high-speed-data-project/>

From the information provided above, we can conclude that the press release has reached a wide audience, **resulting in more than 300.000 visits during the first month of the project.**

ANNEX I: PRESS RELEASE

Creating the fastest outdoor wireless Internet connection in the world

18 December 2014 06:58

Lancaster University engineers are to head up a European team working on the world's first W-band wireless system, heralding the arrival of cost effective, high speed internet everywhere, every time.

The ground-breaking £2.8 million TWEETHER project, funded by Horizon 2020, the biggest EU research and innovation programme ever, will set an important milestone in 'millimeter wave technology' for high speed wireless mobile and fixed point Internet.

Millimeter waves - extremely high frequency waves found in the spectrum between microwaves and infrared waves - are deemed to be the most promising and cost effective solution for the future.

The TWEETHER project will result in a powerful and compact transmission hub, based on a novel travelling wave tube power amplifier and an advanced chipset in a compact terminal, with performance far outweighing any other technology.

After three years of design and development, the system will be tested in a real operating environment.

The project has been sparked by the huge rise in demand for mobile data, which places unprecedented strains on networks to deliver more and more capacity.

Millions of users are now suffering a 'digital divide' because of the very limited availability of high data rate in most residential, sub urban or rural areas, where optical fibre, often slow and expensive to install, is not available.

"The enormous flux of data transferred via wireless networks, increasing at a super-high pace, makes today's state-of-the-art networks quickly outdated, says Lancaster University's Professor of Electronics Claudio Paoloni, who is also the Project Co-ordinator.

"The huge spread of portable smart phone, tablets and the increasing demand of services hungry for data, such as high definition TV, videoconferencing and online games, are posing formidable challenges with the congestion of the available spectrum and the limits of present technology."

Professor Paoloni said the answer was the exploitation of unused portions of the spectrum but at higher frequencies.

The recent outstanding advancements in the field of vacuum electron devices and solid state electronics using millimetre wave frequencies opens the route for the breakthrough in wireless high speed data communications.

Lancaster University leads a European consortium including one of largest suppliers of vacuum tubes, Thales Electron Devices (France), four SMEs including Bluwan (France), OMMIC (France), HFSE (Germany) and Fibernova (Spain) and two other universities, Goethe University Frankfurt (Germany) and Universitat Politecnica de Valencia (Spain) to successfully tackle these formidable challenges.

The project will be officially launched on campus on 15 January 2015 when Professor Andy Sutton, the Principal Network Architect at EE, will address the session open to the public with a talk entitled 'The role of W-band millimeter wave radio systems in next generation mobile networks backhaul'.

Prof. Andy Sutton, Principal Network Architect at EE, will address the session open to the public with the talk ""The role of W-band millimetre wave radio systems in next generation mobile networks backhaul".

Link: <http://www.lancaster.ac.uk/news/articles/2014/creating-the-fastest-outdoor-wireless-internet-connection-in-the-world/>

ANNEX II: PRESS RELEASE (Spanish)

La Universitat Politècnica de València participa en un proyecto europeo que hará posible el despliegue de las redes inalámbricas del futuro

- El Centro de Tecnología Nanofotónica de la UPV es uno de los socios del proyecto Tweether, financiado por la Comisión Europea a través del programa Horizon 2020.
- La red Tweether permitirá a los operadores ofrecer acceso ubicuo a Internet de gran ancho de banda con un coste de despliegue mínimo. Estas características permitirán reducir la brecha digital y ofrecer a los usuarios finales servicios de valor añadido (servicios multimedia, telemedicina, teleformación, etc.).

Poner a disposición de todo el mundo conexiones inalámbricas a Internet de alta velocidad y a muy bajo coste. Este es el objetivo final de Tweether, un proyecto financiado por la Comisión Europea a través del programa Horizon 2020, entre cuyos socios se encuentra la Universitat Politècnica de València. La meta es proporcionar capacidades de varios Gigabits por segundo para soportar las redes de acceso inalámbricas de nueva generación (4G y en un futuro 5G) lo que permitirá ofrecer altas velocidades de transmisión a un mayor número de usuarios. El proyecto ha comenzado este mes de enero y se extenderá hasta 2017.

La red Tweether proporcionará mayor ancho de banda, cobertura y capacidad que la que ofrecen las redes inalámbricas de distribución actuales, lo que redundará en que los usuarios podrán disfrutar de servicios de alto valor añadido (multimedia, telemedicina, teleformación, etc.) con una gran calidad.

Para conseguirlo, los socios de este proyecto, que está coordinado por la Universidad de Lancaster, desarrollarán un nuevo sistema de red inalámbrica punto-multipunto aprovechando un espectro no utilizado actualmente. La red operará en la banda de milimétricas en la región de 90 GHz.

“La eclosión del uso de teléfonos inteligentes, tabletas y la creciente demanda de datos asociados a servicios como la televisión de alta definición (HDTV), videoconferencias o juegos en línea, plantean enormes desafíos debido a la congestión del espectro disponible y los límites de la tecnología actual. Así, las ondas milimétricas que se encuentran en el espectro entre las microondas y las ondas de terahercios son la única solución para poder responder a estos desafíos”, apunta Ruth Vilar, investigadora del Centro de Tecnología Nanofotónica de la Universitat Politècnica de València.

Asimismo, al tratarse de una red de comunicación punto-multipunto, Tweether dará servicio desde una estación base a varias áreas. “La conjunción de transmisiones punto-multipunto y el desarrollo de amplificadores de alta potencia, circuitos integrados avanzados, antenas, etc. en la banda de frecuencias de 90GHz permitirá dar un paso más para universalizar el despliegue de redes inalámbricas de alta velocidad. Ayudará también a reducir la brecha digital, que provoca que millones de usuarios en todo el mundo -fundamentalmente de zonas residenciales, suburbanas o rurales donde no se puede desplegar fibra óptica- no tengan acceso a Internet”, destaca Ruth Vilar.

El proyecto cuenta además con el asesoramiento de Everything Everywhere (EE), Telecom Italia, Deutsche Telecom y Orange Lab, que ayudarán a identificar las necesidades del mercado para, a partir de ellas, definir las especificaciones finales de la red.

El Centro de Tecnología Nanofotónica de la UPV participará en la definición de la red, así como en la integración de todos los componentes de la red. Además, acogerá a la finalización del proyecto el despliegue y validación de la nueva red inalámbrica Tweether.

ANNEX III: EXAMPLES OF PRESS RELEASE PUBLICATIONS

Creating the fastest outdoor wireless Internet connection in the world

18 December 2014

Microtechnics/Electroengineering

Lancaster University engineers are to head up a European team working on the world's first W-band wireless system, heralding the arrival of cost effective, high speed internet everywhere, every time.

Link:

http://www.myscience.org.uk/wire/creating_the_fastest_outdoor_wireless_internet_connection_in_the_world-2014-lancaster&rss=1

Creating the fastest outdoor wireless Internet connection in the world

18 December 2014 Lancaster University

Lancaster University engineers are to head up a European team working on the world's first W-band wireless system, heralding the arrival of cost effective, high speed internet everywhere, every time.

Link: <http://www.alphagalileo.org/ViewItem.aspx?ItemId=148384&CultureCode=en>

Creating the world's fastest outdoor wireless Internet connection

19 December 2014

Lancaster University engineers are to head up a European team working on the world's first W-band wireless system, heralding the arrival of ubiquitous, high speed internet.

The ground-breaking £2.8 million TWEETHER project, funded by Horizon 2020, will set an important milestone in 'millimetre wave technology' for high speed wireless mobile and fixed point Internet.

Millimetre waves - extremely high frequency waves found in the spectrum between microwaves and infra-red waves - are deemed to be the most promising and cost effective solution for the future.

Link: <http://www.dpaonthenet.net/article/88426/Creating-the-world-s-fastest-outdoor-wireless-Internet-connection.aspx>

Tech/Networks/Networking

WORLD'S 'FASTEST WIRELESS NETWORK' TO ARRIVE IN LANCASTER

Networking

by Amy-jo Crowley | 19 December 2014

Scientists are paving the way for the fastest performing Internet at affordable costs.

The first millimetre wave (W-band) wireless network system, said to be the 'world's fastest', is being tested at Lancaster University, paving the way for high-speed Internet at affordable costs.

Link: <http://www.cbronline.com/news/tech/networks/networking/worlds-fastest-wireless-network-to-arrive-in-lancaster-4473833>

SCIENTIFIC BLOGGING
SCIENCE 2.0

W-Band Wireless: High Speed Internet, Outdoors And Everywhere

By News Staff | December 19th 2014 08:00 AM | [Print](#) | [E-mail](#) | [Track Comments](#)

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A European team is working on the world's first W-band wireless system - millimeter wave technology for high speed wireless mobile and fixed point Internet - as part of a £2.8 million TWEETHER project.

Millimeter waves - found in the spectrum between microwaves and infrared waves - are considered the most promising and cost effective solution for the future. The TWEETHER project will result in a powerful and compact transmission hub, based on a traveling wave tube power amplifier and an advanced chipset in a compact terminal, with

performance far outweighing any other technology.

Link:

http://www.science20.com/news_articles/wband_wireless_high_speed_internet_outdoors_and_everywhere-151636

Deliverable D7.1

W-band wireless broadband system aims to streamline services

21 January 2015 | By Julia Pierce

Print | Email | Share | Comments (1) | Save

Rural blackspots and network congestion could end thanks to a new wireless high-speed data communications system under development by a European team led by engineers at Lancaster University.

The £2.8m EU-funded TWEETHER project aims to develop a W-band wireless broadband system to provide cost effective, high speed internet with a capacity up to 10Gbps and distribution of hundreds of Mbps to tens of terminals. This will allow current capacity and coverage challenges to be overcome.

The system will exploit unused portions of the spectrum utilising millimetre waves - extremely high frequency waves found between microwaves and infrared waves and will include a powerful and compact transmission hub, based on a novel travelling wave tube power amplifier and an advanced chipset in a compact terminal, with performance far outweighing any other technology.

'The breakthrough of TWEETHER project is a novel wireless PmP (Point to multipoint) system that integrates a novel, compact, low cost and high yield Traveling Wave Tube (TWT) power amplifier at the transmission hub, to power an affordable high performance transceiver,' said Claudio Paoloni, project co-ordinator and Lancaster University professor of electronics.

Specifications will be developed by operators including EE, Deutsche Telekom, Telecom Italia and Spain's Aertis. Once these are in place, the team - which includes Thales Electron Devices, four SMEs including Bluwan, OMMIC, HFSE and Fibernova, Goethe Frankfurt University and Politecnica de Valencia - will start the design of the different components. These include a W-band traveling wave tube, multi-GHz band MMIC (Monolithic Microwave Integrated Circuit) chipset and a synthesiser.

After three years of design and development, the system will be tested at the University Politecnica de Valencia's campus, the first ever test for a W-band transceiver.

Link: <http://www.theengineer.co.uk/news/w-band-wireless-broadband-system-aims-to-streamline-services/1019762.article#ixzz3Pa91XbWk>

Deliverable D7.1

